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World Civilizations II D

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Passenger Elevator

The Otis Safety Lift was the first modern elevator. Invented by Elisha Otis in 1852, the Safety Lift used an advanced braking mechanism which locked the lift in place in the event of the supporting wire breaking. He was a master mechanic at the time; working at a bed factory where heavy materials often had to be lifted. He designed the mechanism to prevent the factories hoist from falling if the cable broke. This mechanism was demonstrated in a *coup de theatre* at a public unveiling at the 1853 World's Fair in New York. Otis, in a flamboyant and eccentric demonstration of his invention's capability and to the observing crowd's horror, had the rope suspending a platform he was standing on cut. He, having not fallen to his death, pronounced to the world "All safe, gentlemen, all safe!" The safety lift sparked the revolution not only in elevator technology but also in the urbanization of modern society.

The development of the passenger elevator in the late nineteenth century turned the conception of urban environments on its head. It "enabled the development of buildings over 10 storeys high in mid-19th century American cities, where the growth of urban commerce brought pressure on limited real estate. The invention of the safety lift by Elisha Otis made buildings above five storeys workable." An example of this is one of the first skyscrapers ever built. "The 10-storey Home Insurance Company Building, completed in Chicago in 1885, is regarded as the

first modern skyscraper.”¹ It was built during a period of reconstruction after the Great Chicago Fire in 1871. “In addition to being the first of a new generation of steel-framed skyscrapers built in cities across America and the world, the building set the standard for various other building innovations, including rapid, safe elevators, wind bracing and modern plumbing.”² It is clear that the passenger elevator is responsible for early skyscrapers and the innovations and societal changes resulting from it.

The passenger elevator is often taken for granted because of its ubiquity. Most people, especially those residing in urban environments assume that elevators have always existed. The passenger elevator is a technology we use every day and life would be very different without them. Tall buildings would be infeasible if it were not for the elevator. “Without safe lifts, skyscrapers would not have been built.”³ Skyscrapers were a prime cause of the urbanization revolution. It allowed for many times greater floor space than the amount of space on the ground.

The Empire State Building is a prime example of the efficiency of three-dimensional urban environments. It had in excess of one hundred floors, meaning that there is a roughly one hundred times increase in usable space for the same footprint. It has a floor area of 2,768,591 sq ft; while its base is only 2 acres. The Empire State Building currently holds 73 cable elevators, hauling people up and down the building all day and night to their work. There are around one thousand businesses operating in the building, employing around 21,000 people. The efficiency in the utilization of space is incredible. The amount of usable space that would have existed without a skyscraper is one city block. The Empire State building has the equivalent of nineteen

¹ [In class book. P. 108. “Electricity on the move”](#)

² [History.com Home Insurance Building](#)

³ [Inventing the 19th Century: 100 Inventions that Shaped the Victorian Age by Stephen van Dulken](#)

city blocks of floor space. “We don't tend to think of elevators as mass transportation systems, but they are: they move hundreds of millions of people everyday... The fact that so many people can work together in huge buildings on compact sites is possible only because of the elevator.”

It is through Urbanization movement that many modern innovations were created. Urban centers are focal points of human development. When many businesses and institutions are packed together in a small space it is only natural for a higher than normal number of opportunities to be present. People are attracted to cities because of their multitude of opportunities. “They're creative, as measured by a high output of patents and a high rate of startups. They're rich, as measured by economic output per person. And relative to rural and suburban areas, they are environmental utopias, with low rates of energy use per person and low consumption of gasoline. This minor miracle—wealth, creativity, and vitality in a modest environmental footprint—would be impossible without the elevator.” Urban centers are also efficient in terms of pollution per person. Although this may at first seem counterintuitive because of the environmental harm coming from cities, public transportation as well as other shared public resources. “More than 80 percent of Manhattanites travel to work by subway, or by bike or on foot, ten times the rate for America as a whole. A similar story can be told for high-rise cities across the planet from Singapore to Sydney.”⁴ Urban environments are not a symptom of societal innovation; it is the cause of it.

Megacities show no signs of slowing down in growth. As population and innovation increases, so will the floor space required to contain it. In new and already developed cities there is a very limited amount of available space. Larger and larger skyscrapers are being built

⁴ [Fifty Inventions That Shaped the Modern Economy by Tim Harford](#)

reaching thousands of feet into the sky. The limiting factor of the height of the buildings is the constraints of the modern elevator. Most elevators are suspended using steel cables along a shaft. The problem with this system is that the cables are so long and heavy they can't hold themselves, let alone an elevator. German elevator giant ThyssenKrupp's brand new elevator called "Multi" is groundbreaking. The Multi uses no cables whatsoever. Instead, the cab is suspended and propelled using linear induction motors.⁵ Linear induction motors are similar to traditional electric motors because they both utilize the properties of electromagnetism. The motor is very similar to MagLev and monorail train propulsion system. The elevator system's lack of cables overcomes a multitude of issues. With linear induction elevators, there is no reason to limit the number of elevators or confine them to a single shaft because there are no cables to get in the way. The lack of cables also solves the problem with height limits with cable cars. There is theoretically no height limit because there is no heavy cable to weigh it down. The Multi elevator also has the ability to move horizontally through horizontal shafts. It can move throughout a whole network of elevator shafts, not just a single vertical one.

Buildings are currently designed, whether consciously or not, around the concept of elevators moving only vertically because it is the elevator that is the grounding centerpiece and enabler of skyscrapers' accessibility. This technology is a paradigm shift that will revolutionize building accessibility and design. Elevator technology is becoming more and more similar to the Turbolift, a fictional elevator used on starships in the *Star Trek* universe.⁶ These elevators have the capability of moving not only vertically, but also horizontally through the ship at high speeds

⁵ [ThyssenKrupp Multi Elevator](#)

⁶ [Turbolift](#)

as well. The passenger elevator is a technology that continues to evolve to fulfill the requirements of modern society.

The worldwide impact of the passenger elevator is clear. It is the elevator that allowed for the advent of urbanization. “The urban population of the world has grown rapidly from 746 million in 1950 to 3.9 *billion* in 2014.”⁷ These urban centers have been the center of social, cultural, and economic development for the past century. The elevator is a prerequisite to other modern innovations as these innovations would be out of context without urban centers and the developments resulting from them. An example of this is the internal combustion engine. Although motor vehicles enabled the easy transport of people, its benefit assumes a meaningful destination. Without urbanization there would be no reason to drive around; no reason to leave small-scale rural society as there would be nowhere to go. These advances for the human race would not have existed if there were never a passenger elevator. Elevators are a paramount technology as their utilization and sophistication are increasing. Elevators are also assured to be utilized for a long-lasting time frame. The impact of the elevator is global, affecting every person on the planet both directly and indirectly. The significance of the elevator’s impact will stretch far into the future as elevators and the structures that contain them continue to evolve.

⁷ [World’s population increasingly urban with more than half living in urban areas - UN](#)